

A corpus-assisted analysis of attitudinal appraisals in selected newspaper reports on domestic violence in Nigeria and Uganda

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Abstract: The rate of domestic violence globally has continued to rise, with its severe impacts in Africa due to persistent socioeconomic challenges. This study examines how domestic violence is discursively represented in Nigerian and Ugandan newspapers, with data drawn primarily from The Nation (Nigeria) and Daily Monitor (Uganda), covering publications between March and May 2020. Martin and White's (2010) Appraisal Framework, which investigates the deployment of Attitude resources, was adopted as a framework. The findings reveal that Affect Attitude is mostly deployed in both corpora. While the Ugandan newspaper foregrounds negative Affect, the Nigerian newspaper prioritises positive Affect. Although both countries employ negative Propriety and Normality, positive Judgment is mainly realised in both contexts through Capacity. Meanwhile, Appreciation is the least utilised Attitude type. Ugandan newspaper deploys positive Appreciation through composition (balance) and valuation, with negative Appreciation centering on reaction (impact and quality). In contrast, Nigerian newspapers rely on valuation and reaction (impact) for both positive and negative Appreciation. The study concludes that media discourse in both contexts does more than just report domestic violence. It also constructs emotional meanings, assigns moral influence, and evaluates social responses to domestic violence during the COVID-19 pandemic.

Keywords: Attitude appraisal, Corpus-assisted, COVID-19, Domestic violence, Nigeria, Uganda, Newspaper reports

1. Introduction

The multifaceted nature of domestic violence (DV) comes with several consequences for both the individuals and society. In the past, many studies have examined different forms of discrimination and violence, particularly intimate partner violence, in non-African contexts. Notable examples include research conducted in the United Kingdom (Stanko, 2000a), Russia (Post, 2000), and Japan (Kozu, 1999), where scholars have explored the patterns, causes, and societal responses to intimate partner violence within their respective socio-cultural settings. These studies reinforce the global nature of domestic violence and provide a broader context for understanding its dynamics across different societies. While domestic violence is highly prevalent in Africa, as noted by Watts and Zimmerman (2002), it remains a global issue with serious effects on individuals, families, and communities. Studies in Nigeria have revealed that domestic violence has consistently been rooted in patriarchal structure, coupled with societal silence and weak judicial systems (Ojemeiri et al., 2024). Further studies have shown that socio-economic hardship, unemployment, and financial dependency can intensify domestic violence and restrict victims' ability to seek help (Umukoro & Okurame, 2022). Additionally, Suleiman and Danyawo (2025) also show that domestic violence is often normalised within intimate relationships, with both structural and cultural factors contributing to its persistence. Furthermore, recent scholarship has revealed that Nigerian media often rely on gendered assumptions and selective framing to shape public perceptions of perpetrators and victims (Akinseye 2024, 2025a, 2025b). Similarly, Asuinura and Kipo-Sunyehzi (2024), together with Akinola (2023), highlight how entrenched gender inequalities and patriarchal power relations continue to shape experiences,

representations of violence, and gendered discourse across African societies. They further argue that such gendered communication patterns reinforce social vulnerability and inequality, thereby underscoring the importance of critically examining how media discourse constructs and reproduces power dynamics in the reporting of domestic violence. Meanwhile, in Africa, the 2020 COVID-19 pandemic worsened the domestic violence cases due to economic downturns, restricted access to support systems, and prolonged household confinement. At this point, the United Nations flagged the surge, while noting that such has increased the financial pressures on families and individuals. Given this context, therefore, understanding the attitude of the media during this period became critical as it would help address the domestic violence social effects.

Additionally, in almost all African societies, domestic violence within the confines of the family is frequently considered a private matter, and this cultural view has downplayed it as a serious social issue. However, during the coronavirus pandemic, many people faced isolation, while others had financial difficulties and loss of jobs, which eventually led to escalating conflicts within households. In Nigeria, the World Bank reported that about 83 million people, which is approximately 40% of the population, have experienced economic hardship below the poverty line (National Bureau of Statistics, 2020; World Bank, 2020), while Uganda's poverty rate rose from 19.7% in 2017 to 21.4% in 2020 due to pandemic-related pressures. Also, the Ugandan demographic data in 2020 revealed that 56% of married women aged 15-49 have experienced either physical or sexual violence by a husband (Uganda Bureau of Statistics, 2021). It was also noted that among the women who had endured gender-based violence (GBV), only a small number reported incidents to the police (Uganda Bureau of Statistics, 2021).

Despite these alarming statistics, critical questions remain insufficiently addressed: How is domestic violence constructed and represented in media discourse in Nigeria and Uganda? What evaluative meanings are embedded in these representations? And how do these representations shape public understanding of domestic violence during crisis periods such as the COVID-19 pandemic?

Thus, while many people still consider domestic violence as a personal matter, the media is playing an important role in shaping public awareness and influencing societal responses to cases of domestic violence in Uganda and Nigeria. For instance, the public, through the media reports, has raised awareness about the severity of domestic violence, situating it within a broader public health crisis narrative. Therefore, to examine how the media construct these perceptions, this study is guided by the following research questions:

- i. What evaluative language (affect, judgment, and appreciation) is used in these representations?
- ii. What similarities and differences exist in the evaluative framing of domestic violence across the two contexts?

2. Theory

Appraisal Theory focuses on analysing evaluative language. It examines how speakers use language to convey emotions/feelings, judgments, and appreciations. This theory was developed over the past few decades by Martin and White (2010). Although initially, it was partly driven by educational initiatives, such as Australia's genre-based literacy programs, it has been applied in fields beyond literacy requirements across disciplines, including science, media, and the arts. Its adaptability in media studies makes it relevant to news discourse and other business research. The theory is a subset of Functional Grammar, and in particular, the interpersonal metafunction, which expands upon the social meanings traditionally studied within SFG. The theory has been tested across disciplines and has undergone refinements and updates. Its structure has three main subsystems: Attitude, Engagement, and Graduation. These systems help in the analysis of evaluative language in texts and allow researchers to explore how language constructs social and emotional relationships. First, the Attitude subsystem shows how language expresses positive or negative evaluations. Attitude Appraisal can further be divided into three categories: Affect Attitude, Satisfaction, and Desirability. Secondly, the Judgment Attitude examines human behavior concerning social norms and moral standards. Judgment subtypes include Normality,

Capacity, Tenacity, Veracity, and Propriety, each assessing behavior's acceptability or morality. Finally, the third one is the Appreciation Attitude, which investigates objects and processes. It assesses Reaction (immediate impact and quality), Composition (balance and complexity), and Valuation (worth or significance).

Figure 1: The Appraisal Theory Framework (Martin and White, 2010)

Several past studies have applied Appraisal Theory in different fields. For instance, Prastikawati (2021) analysed emotional undertones in BBC News articles, and the findings revealed ‘unhappiness’ as the dominant theme. Similarly, Khoo et al. (2012) highlighted the attitudinal perspective on the online news text. The result found that attitudinal terms used in it, such as appreciation and judgment, were the most frequently used appraisal resources. Also, Sodiq, Sophia and Hidayat (2022) examine the evaluative shifts in translated literature. The findings suggest that cultural factors influenced how characters were portrayed in Indonesian-to-English translations. Furthermore, Chalimah et al. (2018) investigate the cultural biases in media coverage of religious conflicts and showcased its role in influencing public perceptions. Similarly, Wu (2013) observes that public service ads in advertising often employ Judgment to shape audience attitudes by prioritising moral evaluations over emotional appeals. Finally, in an educational context, Akinseye (2021) examines that students’ essays have a variety of attitudinal functions with more Affect values, which are expressed implicitly as positive and negative values

Thus, while these previous studies demonstrate the applicability of the theory, its potential in examining social issues such as domestic violence remains underexplored. Therefore, the study examines how newspapers in Nigeria and Uganda use Attitude Appraisal to shape public attitudes toward domestic violence.

3. Research methodology

The study's data were sourced from LexisNexis. Newspaper articles on domestic violence were primarily sourced from The Nation (Nigeria) and Daily Monitor (Uganda), selected due to their wide national circulation, credibility, and representativeness of mainstream media discourse in their respective countries, covering publications between March and May 2020. The data period coincides with the period of the first wave of COVID-19, a period marked by increased reports of domestic violence due to lockdowns, economic strain, and restricted access to support systems. For the analysis, 56 articles were selected from Uganda, while Nigeria's corpus included 64 articles. Articles were selected based on their explicit focus on domestic violence, while duplicates, irrelevant reports, and non-news items were excluded. The sourcing made use of the following keywords: domestic violence, gender-based violence, domestic abuse, and intimate partner violence. After data collection, the corpora from the two countries were cleaned to remove metadata and afterward uploaded into a corpus tool. Sketch Engine, a comprehensive corpus analysis tool that enables the identification of common terms and concordances, was used. The corpus tool enabled the systematic extraction of recurrent lexical patterns and evaluative meanings that would otherwise remain obscured in manual analysis. After sorting, a specialised corpus of 41,880 tokens for Nigeria and 32,288 for Uganda was compiled. To focus on attitudinal expressions, word lists were filtered by parts of speech, specifically the classes of adjectives and verbs, to capture words related to Attitude, Judgments, and Appreciations.

4. Presentation of Results, Analyses, and Findings

Attitudes in Media Coverage of Domestic Violence in Uganda and Nigeria

The results in the table below show the summary of *Affect*, *Judgment*, and *Appreciation* Attitudes in the selected Ugandan and Nigerian newspaper reportage on domestic violence during the first wave of COVID-19. To fully understand the situation, the results show both positive and negative Attitudinal Appraisal.

Table 1: Attitude Types in Domestic Violence Coverage During COVID-19

Attitude Type	Uganda Positive	Uganda Negative	Nigeria Positive	Nigeria Negative
Affect	51.94%	60.90%	66.61%	69.70%
Judgment	28.17%	20.42%	20.03%	16.74%
Appreciation	19.90%	18.68%	13.36%	13.56%
Total	100%	100%	100%	100%

The table above (Table 1) shows that *Affect Attitude* (Positive and Negative) is the predominantly deployed Attitude type in both countries. In Nigeria, both positive and negative *Affect* attitude is higher, while Uganda is showing slightly lower coverage in both positive and negative *Affect* attitudes. Though there is a slight difference in the *Affect Attitude* of both countries, there is no doubt that both nations focus on the emotional and psychological toll of domestic violence. Furthermore, the *Judgment* Attitudes constitute the next prevalent type. The result shows that the positive and negative judgment attitudes in Uganda are higher than in Nigeria. Lastly, the *Appreciation* Attitudes appear least frequently in both contexts, though the positive and the negative *Appreciation* Attitudes are dominantly deployed in Uganda than in Nigeria. From the table above, the distribution across the *Affect*, *Judgment*, and *Appreciation* Attitudes not only recognises the emotional impact of on the issue of domestic violence, but it also holds a critical view on the conditions surrounding it.

Negative and Positive Affect Attitudes in Ugandan and Nigerian Newspaper Reportage on Domestic Violence

Descriptions of personal emotion are referred to as Affect. Table 2 below presents the Affective markers in the newspaper reportage of domestic violence in Uganda and Nigeria. It highlights five specific Affect markers that reveal the emotional attitudes in the two contexts.

Table 2: Affect Type Expressions in Domestic Violence Coverage During COVID-19

Affect Type	Uganda Positive	Uganda Negative	Nigeria Positive	Nigeria Negative
Dis/inclination	27.18%	19.08%	20.48%	17.60%
Un/happiness	12.14%	33.53%	14.76%	17.07%
IN/security	27.18%	19.08%	17.84%	13.33%
Dis/satisfaction	16.02%	16.76%	16.52%	22.40%
Un/desirability	17.48%	11.56%	30.39%	29.60%
Total	100%	100%	100%	100%

In Uganda, the highest positive Affect markers were *Dis/inclination* and *IN/Security*, both at 27.18%. The highest negative Affect type was *Un/happiness*, accounting for 33.53% of negative expressions, reflecting a significant focus on distressing attitudes. *Dis/satisfaction* was the next, with 16.02% positive and 16.76% negative markers, while *Un/desirability* markers were the lowest, with 17.48% positive and 11.56% negative occurrences. On the other hand, Nigerian newspaper reportage has *Un/desirability* as the most prominent marker of Affect Attitude, which accounted for 30.39% of positive expressions and 29.60% of negative expressions. After that was *Dis/inclination*, which made up 20.48% of positive and 17.60% of negative markers. Meanwhile, other Affect types, *Un/happiness*, were balanced, with 14.76% positive and 17.07% negative occurrences, while *IN/security* registered 17.84% positive and 13.33% negative. *Dis/satisfaction* in Nigeria had 16.52% positive and 22.40% negative expressions, underscoring prevalent themes of dissatisfaction. Affect words and their frequency from the corpus. The distribution above reveals differences in how domestic violence is emotionally constructed in both countries. While both contexts show high levels of negative attitudes, Uganda demonstrates a stronger emphasis on vulnerability and insecurity, whereas Nigeria shows a stronger emphasis on suffering, harm, and behavioural disruption. Therefore, to further illustrate how these Affective patterns are realised attitudinally, the following lists present the specific negative and positive.

List 1: List of Negative Affect Attitudes in Nigerian and Ugandan Newspaper Reportage on Domestic Violence

Affect Type	Negative Affect and Frequency in Nigeria	Negative Affect and Frequency in Uganda
Dis/inclination	Suicidal (9), Scary(6), Afraid(3), Hapless(2), Suffer(21), Struggle (10), Hate(5), Regret(3), Neglect(2), Worry(2), Panic(1), Flee(1), Detest(1)	Annoyed(2), Afraid(1), Desperate(1), Accuse(d) (21), Scare(2), Offend(2), Deny(2), Surrender(1), Nag(1)
Un/happiness	Bad(13), Wicked(3), Sad(3), Depressed(2), Angry(2), Forlorn(1), Hurtful(1), Unhappy(1), Unsettling(1), , Condemn(9), Depress (6), Traumatize(3), Bemoan(2), Agonize(2), Mourn(1), Frustrate(1), Agitate(1)	Vulnerable(23), Sad(4), Resigned(2), Lonely(1), Gloomy(1), Stressful(1), Suffer(9), Cry(6), Worsen(5), Regret(2), Intimidate(2), Sadden(1), Traumatise(1)

IN/security	Harmful(5), Helpless(3), Hypervigilant (2), Furious(1), Tense(1), Volatile(1), Abuse(14), Assault(7), Stab(5), Infect(4), Ravage(2), Undermine(2), Paralyze(1), Fear(1), Deter(1), vulnerable (24)	Poor(12), Anxious(2), Helpless(2), Unsafe(2), Grim(1), Irritable(1), Fail(5), Worry(4), Scare(2), Harass(1) Overwhelm(1)
Dis/satisfaction	Poor(8), Unfortunate(5), Dastardly(3), Unbearable(2), Shameful(2), Ashamed(1), Degrading(1), Unpleasurable(1), Useless(1), Poor(8), Lose(27), Cause(10), Provoke(5), Ruin(3), Contaminate(2), Destroy(2), Obliterate(1), Fester(1), Deprive(1)	Unbearable(4), Overwhelming(2) Distasteful(2)Distressing(1)Blame(7)Shock(5)Mistreat (4)Criticize(2)Hurt(1)Misuse(1)
Un/desirability	Dangerous(8), Deadly(5), Sorry(3), Crass(2), Terrifying(2), Sadistic(1), Bleak(1), Disgraceful(1), Unsympathetic(1), refuse(6), avoid(8), suffer(21), Hate(5), abuse(14), decline(4), worsen(5), complain(6), traumatize(3), escalate(3) dishearten(2), neglect(2), undermine(2), detest(1), harass(1), denigrate(1), Vilify(1), scorn(1), mock(1)	Horrible(4), Greedy(2), Fake(1), Frightening(1), Terrible(1), Detain (7), degrade(2), oppose(2), punish(1)

List 2: List of Positive Affect Attitudes in Nigerian and Ugandan Newspaper Reportage on Domestic Violence

Affect Type	Positive Affect and Frequency in Nigeria	Positive Affect and Frequency in Uganda
Inclination	Able(19), Committed(5), Interested(3), Concerned(2), Hope(9), Prefer(6) Embrace(3), Motivate(2), Aspire(2), Muster(1)Appreciate(1), help(36), Inspire(1)	Committed (4), Supportive(1), Help(34), Appreciate(8), Care(4), Like(2), Invite(2), Hope(1), Encourage(1)
Happiness	Great1(1), Glorious(5), Happy(3), Grateful(2), Loving(2), Fortunate(1), Helpful (1), Warm(1), Cheerful(1), Love(17), Please(9), Enjoy(4), Trust(3), Encourage(2), Laud(2), Endear(1), Console(1), Delight(1)	Optimistic(3), Happy(2), Sweet(2), Fortunate(1), Tolerant(1), Love(6), Enjoy(4), Smile(2), Aid(2), Hearten(1), Laugh(1)
Security	Calm(7), Safe(7), Sure(3), Reassuring(4), Patient(1), Sound(1), Mindful(1), Feel(15), Celebrate(8), Pray(5), Endure(3), Overcome(2), Sustain(2), Ease(1), Safeguard(1), Calm(1), Support(19)	Safe(15), Peaceful(3), Vigilant(1), Aware(1), Indispensable(1), Support(23), Enhance(5), Sustain(3), Obtain(2), Safeguard(1), Calm(1)
Satisfaction	Healthy(10), Reliable(5), Steady(3), Relatable(2), Amazing(2), Flourishing(1),	Productive(4), Hopeful(2), True(2), Sustained(1), Thank(9), Commend(9), Benefit(4),

	Smart(1), Interesting(1), Cherished(1), Healthy(10), Rejoice(14), Gather(9), Serve(6), Benefit(3), Fulfill(2), Guarantee(2), Enhance(1), Reward(1), Assuage(1)	Fulfil(1), Nourish(1)
Desirability	Free(7), Alive(5), Proud(2), Precious(2), Optimistic(1), Okay(1), Humanitarian(1), Lovely(1), Motivational(1), want(41), love(17), encourage(12), celebrate(8), enjoy(4), benefit(3), embrace(3), promise(3), foster(2), approve(2), inspire(3)	Preferred(4), Beautiful(2), Commendable(1), Beneficial(1), Truthful(1), Want(13), Teach(9) Forgive(2), Ameliorate(2), Endear(1)

Figure 1: Sketch engine Concordance line for the most deployed negative Affect Attitude

Figure 2: Sketch engine Concordance line for the most deployed positive Affect Attitude

Example:

- i. Most women are economically dependent on men and are **vulnerable** to domestic violence
- ii. She also **accused** her husband of eloping with another woman.
- iii. As leaders, we have to go to the people, care for them, love them, and **help** them
- iv. The re-focussing of our **support** to Uganda is part of a global exercise that the EU is undertaking to help address this crisis in Africa and beyond,' he added.

From list 1 and the concordance line in figure 1 above, the word 'vulnerable' demonstrates the common framing of women as economically and socially at risk in Uganda's domestic violence context. Example (i) suggests how 'vulnerability' increases susceptibility to harm. This frequent usage of vulnerability not only emphasizes the precarious conditions for women but also suggests the limited societal support, which is compounded by economic reliance on male partners. Furthermore, the word "Accuse" is another mostly deployed negative word in the corpus. This is embedded in the Dis/inclination marker, and it emphasizes the conflicts and accusations of misconduct that often arise in domestic settings, particularly regarding issues like infidelity. Example (ii),

demonstrates how accusations reflect relational grievances that often escalate into violence. Across both Uganda and Nigeria, a range of negative affect attitudes such as words indicating *Dis/satisfaction*, *IN/security*, and *Un/desirability* are frequently deployed in the reportage. It is also important to note that there are other examples of negative words, such as ‘poor, helpless, and degrading,’ that are of equal importance in reflecting themes of economic struggle and the feeling of being trapped or exposed to harm, while words like ‘hate, dangerous, and harmful’ state the intensity of emotional responses and fears in the reportage. Such terms are used to express not only the frustration and dissatisfaction with current circumstances, but also the perceived threats to personal security.

Furthermore, in list 2 and concordance in figure 2 above, the most frequently deployed positive word is ‘help’. The prominence of the word is tied to efforts from other individuals or communities that directly enhance victims' quality of life. Example (i) above uses the positive word ‘help’ to express the leaders' responsibilities towards the citizens who are mostly affected by the pandemic, as well as vulnerable to abuse. Furthermore, a closer view of the concordance lines illustrates the diverse forms of help provided to these people, which are: financial assistance, counseling, and community mediation. Similarly, in example (ii), the word "support" showcases collaborative, large-scale efforts to assist Uganda in handling health and economic challenges. The consistent reference to the word ‘support’ reflects the systemic assistance in addressing societal issues, especially in response to domestic violence and the pandemic. In both contexts, positive Affect Attitudes are commonly expressed, especially in the context of social support and resilience.

Negative and Positive Judgment Attitudes in the selected Ugandan and Nigerian Newspaper Reportage on Domestic Violence

Esteem and Sanction are the two subdivisions of Judgment Attitude. Judgments of esteem consist of evaluations of Normality (a person’s behavior compared with what a culture considers normal, Capacity (the capability of a person), and Tenacity (the dependability of a person). Judgments of sanction are to do with Veracity (the honesty of a person) or Propriety (how well a person’s ethics match those of the culture).

Table 3 is the summary of the judgment attitudes in Nigeria and Uganda’s corpora. The summary provides an insight into the judgmental values shaping domestic violence discourse in both countries during a time of heightened pandemic.

Table 3: Judgment Type in Domestic Violence Coverage during COVID-19

Judgment Type	Uganda Positive % of Total	Uganda Negative % of Total	Nigeria Positive % of Total	Nigeria Negative % of Total
Normality	28.3	28.72	16.92	30.69
Veracity	5.66	5.32	16.15	4.95
Capacity	33.02	18.09	29.23	18.81
Tenacity	15.09	17.02	14.62	11.88
Propriety	17.92	30.85	23.08	33.66

The summary in Table 3 shows how each country deploys *Judgment Attitudes* differently in framing domestic violence during the COVID-19 period. In the table, positive *Normality* is almost equal to negative *Normality* in Uganda, while in Nigeria, however, negative *Normality* significantly outweighs positive *Normality*. The *Veracity* shows that the reportage in Nigeria demonstrates a stronger positive judgment compared to Uganda, while both countries record relatively low negative *Veracity*. Furthermore, *Capacity* Judgment is the most prominent positive judgment type in both countries, while its negative counterpart is considerably lower. For *Tenacity*, Uganda records slightly higher negative than positive judgments. In contrast, Nigeria shows more positive *Tenacity* than negative, though the difference is modest. And finally, *Propriety* was the most deployed

negative judgment category in both countries. Although both countries also show positive Propriety (Uganda 17.92%; Nigeria 23.08%), the much higher negative values outweigh the strong moral condemnation. These patterns provide important insight into the severity and dominant forms of domestic violence represented in both countries. The prominence of negative Propriety in both datasets suggests that domestic violence is framed as a serious issue, while the key difference, however, lies in the stronger presence of negative Normality in Nigeria, which indicates that domestic violence is more frequently constructed as an extreme deviation from acceptable social behaviour.

The Construction of Positive and Negative Judgment Attitudes in Nigerian and Ugandan Newspaper Reportage

This section exemplifies the positive and negative judgment attitudes in Nigerian and Ugandan newspaper reportage on domestic violence. This comparative exploration of word frequency and judgment types sheds light on how each country's newspaper frames domestic violence.

List 3: List of Positive Judgment Attitudes in Nigerian and Ugandan Newspaper Reportage on Domestic Violence

Judgment Type	Positive Judgment and Frequency in Nigeria	Positive words and Frequency in Uganda
Normality	Regular (6), Religious(4), Normal(2), Right-thinking(2), Upright(2), Accountable(1), Respected(1), Capable(1) Usual(1), Govern(2)	Normal(2), Lawful(2), Tend(1), Act(1),
Veracity	Real(7), true(4), transparent(2), factual(1), genuine(1), credible (1), honest(1), sincere(1), known(1), Valid(1), certified(1)	Honest(2), Credible(1)
Capacity	Strong/er(16), Functional(7), Experienced(3), Strategic(2), Advanced(2), Astute(1), Dedicated(1), Talented(1), Vital(1), Excel(2), Win(2)	Able(9), Strong/er(3), Comfortable(2), Useful(1), Practical(1), Capable(3), Talented(2), Effective(2), Competent(1) Maintain(5) Overcome(1), Implore(2), Thrive(1)
Tenacity	Persistent(2), Hard(6), Constant(2), Relentless(2), Maximum(1), Independent(1), Hard-working(1), Prevail(2), Persist(2)	Steadfast (4), Continued(1), Influential(1), Bear(3), Persist(1), Trust(1)
Propriety	Responsible(7), Aware(5), Acclaimed(2), Friendly(2), Faithful(1), Cooperative(1), Honest(1), Virtuous(1), Charitable(1), Aid(2), Respect(3), Commend(4)	Good (9), Proud(2), Law-abiding(1), Proper(1), Inclusive(1), Consider(4), Assist(1), Adjust(1)

List 4: List of Negative Judgment Attitudes in Nigerian and Ugandan Media Coverage of Domestic Violence

Judgement Type	Negative Judgement and Frequency in Nigeria	Negative words and Frequency in Uganda
Normality	Criminal(1), Illegal(1), Satanic(3), Inconspicuous(2), Shameful(2), Obnoxious(1), Incapable(1), Strange(1), Absurd (1), Discriminate(1)	Abnormal(2), Suspected(2), Controversial(1), Extort(1), Masquerade(1), Unknown(1), Undermine(2),
Veracity	Alledged (5)	False(1), Shocking(1), Unfair(1)
Capacity	Sick(5), Disabled(2), Deceitful(2), Lifeless(2), Frail(1), Stupid(1), Diminished(1), Manipulative(1), Violate(2)	Weak(3), Helpless(2), Unable(2), Dependent(1), Insufficient(1), Incompetent(4), Incapable(3), Struggling(2), Inadequate(1), Failing(1), Dismiss(1)
Tenacity	Helpless(3), Callous(2), Destructive(2), Cruel(1), Unstable(1), Insistent(1), Cheat(4), Devastate(2)	Difficult(6), Unfinished(2), Fragile(1), Catastrophic(1), Neglect(4), Obscure(1)
Propriety	Abusive(8), Guilty(5), Evil(2), Incestuous(2), Unlawful(2), Regrettable(1), Hurtful(1), Unscrupulous(1), Abused(1), Incite(2), Threaten(4)	Bad(5), Wrong(3), Criminal(2), Selfish(1), Brutal(1), Penalise(1), Defy(1)

Figure 3: Sketch engine Concordance line for the positive judgment attitude

Figure 4: Sketch engine Concordance line for the negative judgment attitude

Example :

- i. You need to be **strong** in the Lord, you need to be enveloped and saturated in His spirit, otherwise your flesh would control your destiny!

- ii. People should be **able** to resolve their problems rather than resort to killing their spouses.
- iii. A late aunt of mine, in her early sixties, died at the hands of her **abusive** husband because she could not bring herself to leave him
- iv. This is normal during such **difficult** times, but be sure to support them to pull through, to calm them down if you sense trauma, and avoid being harsh.

The most deployed *positive capacity*, as seen in the list 3 above, is the word ‘strong’. This is exemplified in example (i), where the word is framed as a strength in terms of resilience through faith. In this context, "strong" emphasizes the belief in religious faith as a vital resource for self-control in overcoming the present affliction (abuse). Another prominent word from the list is "able". Example (ii) encodes Judgment of Capacity, and it evaluates individuals based on their perceived ability to manage conflict constructively. Meanwhile, examples (iii) and (iv) above present ‘abusive’ and ‘difficult’ as significant markers of negative *Judgement Attitude*. It is worthy of note that other prominent negative judgments identified across Uganda and Nigeria, as highlighted in the lists above, reveal the various concerns surrounding domestic violence and the challenges faced by individuals in these contexts. Furthermore, descriptors like *helpless* and *sick* emphasise a sense of despair surrounding victims' situations.

Appreciation Attitudes in Ugandan and Nigerian Newspaper Reportage on Domestic Violence

Appreciation is concerned with the different ways we evaluate all things. This section examines Appreciation Attitudes, which are categorised into Reaction (Impact), Reaction (Quality), Composition (Balance), Composition (Complexity), and Valuation. These categories offer insights into each country’s media perspective on the value, quality, structure, and complexity of responses to domestic violence.

Table 4: Appreciation Type in Domestic Violence Coverage During COVID-19

Below are the Appreciation categories from the corpus of newspaper reportage in Uganda and Nigeria:

Attitude Type	Uganda Positive %	Uganda Negative %	Nigeria Positive %	Nigeria Negative %
Reaction (Impact)	17.11%	21.57%	23.29%	26.53%
Reaction (Quality)	22.37%	23.53%	21.92%	20.41%
Composition (Balance)	27.63%	27.45%	19.18%	16.33%
Composition (Complexity)	9.21%	13.73%	2.74%	4.08%
Valuation	23.68%	13.73%	32.88%	32.65%

From Table 4 above, positive Appreciation reveals differing emphases across both countries. In Uganda, the dominant positive subtype is Composition (Balance) at 27.63%, which is followed by Valuation at 23.68% and Reaction (Quality) at 22.37%, and Reaction (Impact) at 17.11%. In Nigeria, however, Valuation leads at 32.88%, followed by Reaction (Impact) at 23.29%. Furthermore, while Reaction (Quality) is at 21.92%, Composition (Balance) is at 19.18%, which appear at lower levels compared with Uganda. On the other hand, negative Appreciation patterns also show meaningful differences between the two countries. Also in Uganda, the negative Composition (Balance) was mostly deployed, while in Nigeria, negative *Judgement* attitudes are led by *Valuation*, followed by *Reaction (Impact)*. Additionally, the least is the *Composition (Balance)*. Together, this study found that Uganda focuses more on structural balance and quality of responses, whereas Nigeria centres its reportage on significance and the emotional consequences of domestic violence. Appreciation attitudes are constructed in Nigerian and Ugandan media discourse. These differences also reveal how the severity and forms

of domestic violence are constructed in each context. Nigerian reportage has a great emphasis on Valuation and Reaction (Impact). This frames domestic violence as an emotionally intense issue. These patterns are further illustrated in the analysis below.

The Construction of Positive and Negative Appreciation Attitudes in Nigerian and Ugandan Media Reporting on Domestic Violence

This analysis below examines both positive and negative appreciation attitudes in Nigerian and Ugandan media coverage on domestic violence, focusing on the key subtypes and different occurrences of words of appreciation: Reaction (Impact), Reaction (Quality), Composition (Balance), Composition (Complexity), and Valuation.

List 5: List of Positive Appreciation Attitudes in Nigerian and Ugandan Newspaper Reportage on Domestic Violence

Appreciation Type	Negative and Frequency in Nigeria	Negative words and Frequency in Uganda
Reaction (Impact)	Effective (6), Successful (3), Tremendous (2), Amazing (2), Proactive (1), Impactful (1), Bold (1), Massive (1)	Acceptable (4), Powerful (3), Overwhelming (2), Dramatic (1), Valuable (1), Realistic (1), Significant (1)
Reaction (Quality)	Significant (6), Paramount (3), Beautiful (2), Dignified (2), Remarkable (1), Stellar (1), Valuable (1), Meritorious (1)	Positive (7), Super (4), Beautiful (2), Fresh (2), Clean (1), Free (1), Spotless (1)
Composition (Balance)	Equal (6), Balanced (3), Structured (2), Egalitarian (2), Optimum (1)	Special (10), Simple (3), Adequate (3), Bright (2), Sufficient (2), Equitable (1)
Composition (Complexity)	Intricate (1), Enormous (1)	Complete (3), Artistic (1), Profound (1), Immaculate (1), Supplementary (1)
Valuation	Effective (6), Glorious (5), Celebrated (3), Heavenly (2), Worth (2), Fundamental (1), Beneficial (1), Transformative (1), Equitable (1), important (21)	Important (10), Worth (3), Exemplary (2), Right (2), Accurate (1), Priceless (1)

List 6: List of Negative Appreciation Attitudes in Nigerian and Ugandan reportage on Domestic Violence

Appreciation Type	Negative and Frequency in Nigeria	Negative words and Frequency in Uganda
Reaction (Impact)	Difficult (9), Disturbing (3), Tragic (3), Terrible (2), Terrifying (2), Gruesome (1), Threatening (1), Disruptive (1), Unmet (1)	Evil (2), Hostile (2), Unusual (1), Extreme (1), Debatable (1), Deadly (1), Fear (3)
Reaction (Quality)	Wrong (3), Pathetic (2), Indecent (2), Undesirable (2), Gross (1), Degrading (1), Distorted (1), Mediocre (1)	Dirty (4), Satanic (2), Dangerous (2), Infected (1), Noisy (1), Rotten (1), Suicidal (1)
Composition (Balance)	Complex (2), Crude (2), Unfulfilled (2), Controversial (1), Daunting (1)	Muddy (2), Dilapidated (4), Adverse (4), Restricted (2), Bleak (1), Disturbing (1)
Composition (Complexity)	Dysfunctional (1), Mixed (1)	Obstructive (2), Dry (2), Repetitive (1), Ugly (1), Dire (1)
Valuation	Disturbing (3), Malicious (4), Negative (3), Draconian (2), Destructive (2), Obnoxious (1), Degrading (1), Aggravating (1), Malnourished (1)	Cheap (4), Unnoticed (2), Petty (1), Disadvantaged (1), Misuse (1), Shock (1)

Figure 5: Sketch engine Concordance line for the most deployed positive Appreciation Attitude

Figure 6: Sketch engine Concordance line for the negative appreciation attitude

Examples:

- i. One of the facilitators, ASP Kenneth Emegwamor, said the 'workshop is very timely and **important** in this period that domestic violence and sexual violence are on the rise.'
- ii. Yet on the **positive side**, many families have used the time to bond.
- iii. Believe me, if a lot of women were well-prepared emotionally, psychologically, academically, financially, spiritually, IT WOULD BE MOST **DIFFICULT** FOR ANY MAN OR A SATANICALLY-PATRIARCHAL SOCIETY TO ABUSE THEM!
- iv. This creates more fear and anxiety, and if not controlled, could result in **adverse** mental health breakdown, including suicide.

List 5 above shows that the word 'important' is the most deployed marker of Appreciation in the reportage. Furthermore, the concordance line demonstrates that its usage suggests the critical need for addressing domestic violence. To further exemplify this, example (i) above expresses the necessity of timely interventions, such as workshops and support structures, especially during the pandemic lockdown when cases of domestic violence were on the rise. This indicates that the media portrays initiatives related to domestic violence as essential to community welfare and advocates for immediate, structured responses. In example (ii), the word 'positive' is also an instance of Appreciation Attitude, specifically Reaction-Quality. The word introduces an alternative outlook to the dominant reportage on the rise of domestic violence during the pandemic.

From the list of positive *Appreciation* Attitudes above, *Valuation* is the most frequently deployed *Appreciation* category, while Reaction-Quality and Reaction-Impact follow. Furthermore, Composition-Balance and Composition-Complexity, though less frequent, also appear. These patterns show that newspaper reportage consistently frames domestic violence reportage in ways that stress value, impact, quality, and meaningful outcomes.

The negative *Appreciation* Attitude revealed that the words 'difficult' and 'adverse' emerged as the most frequently deployed words. In Nigeria, the word 'difficult' in *Reaction (Impact)* emphasises the pervasive and burdensome challenges individuals face. Example (i) demonstrates this by showing that resisting abuse in a patriarchal society would remain a formidable challenge. Also in Uganda, the word 'adverse' associated with *Composition (Balance)* conveys a sense of harmful imbalance within personal and social conditions, especially concerning mental health and stability. These two words, as exemplified above, describe situations that are not only unfavorable but disrupt equilibrium, leading to heightened anxiety, fear, and instability.

5. Discussion

Understanding the representation of domestic violence in the media is important as newspapers are not only documents for social events and issues, but also actively construct social meanings. This study has been able to unveil, through the lens of the Appraisal Framework, how newspaper reportage encodes different attitudes to frame domestic violence. In light of this, the attitudinal framework becomes a viable tool for identifying how emotional, moral, and evaluative meanings are encoded in newspaper reportage on domestic violence in Uganda and Nigeria during the COVID-19 pandemic. From the analysis, Affect Attitude is the most deployed attitudinal system. This shows that domestic violence reportage in both contexts is primarily framed through positive and negative emotional positioning. Furthermore, while Affect constructs empathy, the Judgment Attitude evaluates behavior. In both countries, the newspapers employ negative Judgment resources of Propriety and Normality to condemn domestic violence. Such a judgment explicitly positions perpetrators as morally culpable, as it reinforces the stance that domestic abuse violates communal expectations of proper conduct. Additionally, the Judgment Attitude is significantly important in both corpora, as Uganda's positive Judgment dominated the reportage in both countries. Finally, Appreciation Attitude reveals balanced but distinct evaluative patterns in Ugandan and Nigerian reportage, as Positive Appreciation is also most evident in both contexts.

6. Conclusion

This study has so far revealed the complex attitudinal portrayal of domestic violence in Ugandan and Nigerian news reportage during the first wave of COVID-19. The analysis revealed the markers that highlight the emotional toll on individuals and society at large. The attitude categories of Affect, judgment, and appreciation collectively emphasise the pressing need for resilience, support, and systemic interventions as both a personal and communal challenge requiring comprehensive attention. This study suggests the contributions of the media and its role in the reportage of domestic violence in Nigerian and Ugandan newspapers. The coverage plays a significant role in shaping public response, while urging communities and policymakers to address domestic violence with both empathy and structural solutions. These further point to individual resilience and societal responsibility, which are important in strengthening the victims.

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